

NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF A SYSTEM OF ORDINARY EQUATIONS WITH A SMALL PARAMETER AT THE HIGHEST DERIVATIVE

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ABSTRACT

Numerical modeling of heterogeneous (multiphase) mixtures or, in particular, gas suspensions (mixtures of gases with solid particles) is one of the important directions in the study of the dynamics of complex hydrodynamic systems. The study of mathematical models of multiphase systems is relevant, primarily from the point of view of applications. Such flows are often encountered in problems of aerodynamics, chemical technology, combustion physics, and others. The study of the influence of suspended particles on the hydrodynamic stability of two-phase flows requires, firstly, a thorough analysis of mathematical models of two-phase media and, secondly, the development of an effective, reliable mathematical apparatus for numerical simulation of hydrodynamic stability equations. In this article, for numerical modeling of the equations of stability of two-phase flows, it is proposed to apply the method of preliminary integration, where Chebyshev polynomials of the first kind are used as basis functions. The essence of the method lies in the fact that before solving the problem, the series in Chebyshev polynomials is pre-integrated the required number of times. Then the integrated series are used in a differential problem and a generalized algebraic eigenvalue problem with complex matrices and vectors is obtained, which is solved by standard methods

Introduction

The use of the spectral and spectral-grid methods for solving the problem of hydrodynamic stability of two-phase flows is described in [1–3]. In these papers, Chebyshev polynomials of the first kind were used as basis functions. Chebyshev polynomials are widely used in the construction of optimal iterative methods, in solving various problems of hydrodynamic stability. Among orthogonal polynomials, only Chebyshev polynomials have a minimax property, which allows more uniform distribution of errors over the entire integration interval. Therefore, all those methods where Chebyshev polynomials are used are optimal or

almost optimal. The range of applications of Chebyshev polynomials is increasingly expanding. Let us give a brief overview of numerical methods for the application of Chebyshev polynomials.

Materials and methods

The hydrodynamic stability of plane-parallel flows with suspended particles is studied with respect to small two-dimensional perturbations in the form of traveling waves:

$$\Psi(x, \eta, t) = \psi(\eta) e^{ik(x-\lambda t)}$$

$$\Phi(x, \eta, t) = \varphi(\eta) e^{ik(x-\lambda t)}$$

Here Ψ, Φ are stream functions, and $\psi(\eta), \varphi(\eta)$ are the amplitudes of the stream function, for pure gas and particles, respectively, x and η are longitudinal and transverse coordinates, t is time, k is the wave number, $\lambda = \lambda_r + i\lambda_i$ is an unknown constant to be determined. If $\lambda_i > 0$, then the flow under consideration is unstable, if $\lambda_i < 0$ - stable. If $\lambda_i = 0$, then the oscillations are neutrally stable.

To represent approximate solutions ψ, φ as series in Chebyshev polynomials of the first kind, we map the integration interval $[\eta_0, \eta_\ell]$ onto the interval $[-1, +1]$ using the following change of the independent variable:

$$\eta = \frac{m}{2} + \frac{\bar{\ell}}{2} y, \quad y \in [-1, +1],$$

$$m = \eta_0 + \eta_\ell, \quad \bar{\ell} = \eta_\ell - \eta_0$$

Thus, we have the following boundary value problem:

$$P\psi + M\varphi = 0, \tag{1}$$

$$S\psi + K\varphi = 0, \tag{2}$$

$$\psi(y) = \varphi(y) = \frac{d\psi}{dy} = 0 \quad \text{at } y = -1, \tag{3}$$

$$\psi(y) = \varphi(y) = \frac{d\psi}{dy} = 0 \quad \text{at } y = 1 \tag{4}$$

where the operators P, M, S, K take the form:

$$P = \frac{1}{ik \bar{\text{Re}}} \bar{D}^2 - (U(y) - \lambda - \frac{if}{GT}) \bar{D} + \frac{d^2 U}{dy^2},$$

$$M = \frac{f}{iGT} \bar{D}, \quad S = \frac{1}{iGT} \bar{D},$$

$$K = -(U(y) - \lambda - \frac{i}{GT}) \bar{D} + \frac{d^2 U}{dy^2},$$

$$\bar{D} = \frac{d^2}{dy^2} - \bar{k}^2, \quad \bar{k} = \frac{\ell}{2} k, \quad \bar{\text{Re}} = \frac{\ell}{2} \text{Re}$$

In the method of preliminary integration, the highest derivatives in differential equations (1) and (2) are represented as the following series:

$$\psi^{(4)}(y) = \sum_{n=0}^{\bar{N}} a_n T_n(y)$$

$$\varphi^{(2)}(y) = \sum_{n=0}^{\bar{N}} d_n T_n(y) \quad (5)$$

$$U(y_p^{(j)}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\bar{N}} b_n T_n(y_p^{(j)})$$

where

$$y_p^{(j)} = \cos(\pi p / \bar{N}), \quad p = 0, 1, \dots, \bar{N}$$

nodes of Chebyshev polynomials, $T_n(y)$ Chebyshev polynomials of the first kind,

\bar{N} - the number of polynomials used to approximate the solution. The expansion coefficients b_n for the main flow in (5) are determined by the following inverse transformation:

$$b_n = \frac{2}{\bar{N} c_n} \sum_{p=0}^{\bar{N}} \frac{1}{c_p} U(y_p^{(j)}) T_n(y_p^{(j)}), \quad n = 0, 1, \dots, \bar{N}$$

$$c_0 = c_{\bar{N}} = 2, \quad c_m = 1 \text{ at } m = 0, \bar{N}.$$

For Chebyshev polynomials, the following recursive formulas are valid:

$$2T_n = \frac{c_n}{n+1} T_{n+1}^{(1)} - \frac{d_{n-2}}{n-1} T_{n-1}^{(1)}, \quad 2yT_n = c_n T_{n+1} + d_{n-1} T_{n-1}, \quad (6)$$

where $c_n = d_n = 0$, if $n < 0$, $c_0 = 2$, $d_0 = 1$,

$$c_n = d_n = 1, \text{ if } n > 0.$$

The main advantage of the pre-integration method is that before solving the boundary value problem (1)-(4), series (5) are pre-integrated. Thus, all lower derivatives and desired solutions are found:

$$\psi^{(3)}, \psi^{(2)}, \psi^{(1)}, \psi, \varphi^{(1)}, \varphi. \quad (7)$$

It is known that integration operations improve the smoothness of series (5). At the same time, in spectral methods, series in Chebyshev polynomials are differentiated.

Using preliminary integration, the functions from (7) are determined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi^{(3)} &= \sum_{j=0}^{\bar{N}+1} \sum_{i=0}^{\bar{N}} f_{ji}^{(3)} a_i T_j + C_1 T_0, \\ \psi^{(2)} &= \sum_{j=0}^{\bar{N}+2} \sum_{i=0}^{\bar{N}} f_{ji}^{(2)} a_i T_j + C_1 T_1 + C_2 T_0, \\ \psi^{(1)} &= \sum_{j=0}^{\bar{N}+3} \sum_{i=0}^{\bar{N}} f_{ji}^{(1)} a_i T_j + \frac{C_1}{4} T_2 + C_1 T_1 + C_2 T_0 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$\psi = \sum_{j=0}^{\bar{N}+4} \sum_{i=0}^{\bar{N}} f_{ji}^{(0)} a_i T_j + \frac{C_1}{24} T_1 + \frac{C_2}{4} T_2 + (C_3 - \frac{C_1}{8}) T_1 + C_4 T_0,$$

$$\varphi^{(1)} = \sum_{j=0}^{\bar{N}+1} \sum_{i=0}^{\bar{N}} \varphi_{ji}^{(1)} d_i T_j + D_1 T_0,$$

$$\varphi = \sum_{j=0}^{\bar{N}+2} \sum_{i=0}^{\bar{N}} \varphi_{ji}^{(0)} d_i T_j + D_1 T_1 + D_2 T_0$$

The constants $C_1, C_2, C_3, C_4, D_1, D_2$ in formulas (8) are determined from the satisfaction of boundary conditions (3) and (4).

Substituting the values of the constants $C_1, C_2, C_3, C_4, D_1, D_2$ into (8) we have the following generalizing formulas

$$\psi^{(\beta)} = \sum_{j=0}^{\bar{N}+4-\beta} \sum_{i=0}^{\bar{N}} g_{ji}^{(\beta)} a_i T_j, \beta = 0, 1, 2, 3, \quad \varphi^{(\beta)} = \sum_{j=0}^{\bar{N}+2-\beta} \sum_{i=0}^{\bar{N}} \bar{g}_{ji}^{(\beta)} d_i T_j, \beta = 0, 1 \quad (9)$$

where, for example

$$g_{ji}^{(3)} = f_{ji}^{(3)} + \delta_{j,0} \frac{3}{2} (\sigma_i^{(0)} - \delta_i^{(0)}) - (\sigma_i^{(1)} + \delta_i^{(1)}),$$

$$\bar{g}_{ji}^{(1)} = \varphi_{ji}^{(1)} + \delta_{j,0} \frac{3}{2} (\varepsilon_i^{(0)} - \Delta_i^{(0)}) - (\varepsilon_i^{(1)} + \Delta_i^{(1)}).$$

other coefficients $g_{ji}^{(\beta)}$ ($\beta = 0, 1, 2$) and $\bar{g}_{ji}^{(0)}$ are also determined.

The found coefficients satisfy the considered boundary conditions and their derivatives. We represent the main flow $U(y)$ as the following row

$$U^{(\beta)}(y) = \sum_{n=0}^{N_{b+1+\beta}} b_n^{(\beta)} T_n(y), \beta = 0, 1, 2, \quad (10)$$

and different values of parameter β correspond to different velocity profiles of the main oncoming flow. For example, at $\beta = 0$ the main flow is the Poiseuille flow:

$$U(y) = 1 - y^2.$$

Thus, substituting series (9)-(10) into equations (1), (2) we have a generalized algebraic eigenvalue problem

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\bar{N}} \frac{1}{ikRe} (\delta_{ik} - 2\bar{k}^2 g_{ik}^{(2)} + k^4 g_{ik}^{(0)}) - \sum_{i=0}^{N_{b+2} \bar{N}+2} \sum_{j=0}^{\bar{N}} \beta_{i\ell_j} b_i^{(0)} g_{ik}^{(2)} + \bar{k}^2 \sum_{i=0}^{N_{b+2} \bar{N}+4} \sum_{j=0}^{\bar{N}} \beta_{i\ell_j} b_i^{(0)} g_{ik}^{(0)} + \sum_{i=0}^{N_b \bar{N}+4} \sum_{j=0}^{\bar{N}} \beta_{i\ell_j} b_i^{(2)} g_{ik}^{(0)} + \frac{\bar{f}}{GT} g_{ik}^{(2)} - \bar{k}^2 g_{ik}^{(0)} a_k + \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{\bar{f}}{iGT} \sum_{k=0}^{\bar{N}} \bar{g}_{ik}^{(2)} - \bar{k}^2 \bar{g}_{ik}^{(0)} d_i = -\lambda \sum_{k=0}^{\bar{N}} \bar{g}_{ik}^{(2)} - \bar{k}^2 \bar{g}_{ik}^{(0)} a_k, i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \bar{N}$$

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\bar{N}} \frac{1}{iGT} (\bar{g}_{ik}^{(2)} - \bar{k}^2 \bar{g}_{ik}^{(0)}) a_k + \frac{\bar{f}}{GT} \sum_{k=0}^{\bar{N}} \bar{g}_{ik}^{(2)} - \bar{k}^2 \bar{g}_{ik}^{(0)} d_i - \sum_{i=0}^{N_{b+2} \bar{N}+2} \sum_{j=0}^{\bar{N}} \beta_{i\ell_j} b_i^{(0)} \bar{g}_{ik}^{(2)} + \bar{k}^2 \sum_{i=0}^{N_{b+2} \bar{N}+4} \sum_{j=0}^{\bar{N}} \beta_{i\ell_j} b_i^{(0)} \bar{g}_{ik}^{(0)} + \sum_{i=0}^{N_b \bar{N}+4} \sum_{j=0}^{\bar{N}} \beta_{i\ell_j} \bar{g}_{ik}^{(2)} d_k = -\lambda \sum_{k=0}^{\bar{N}} \bar{g}_{ik}^{(2)} - \bar{k}^2 \bar{g}_{ik}^{(0)} d_k, i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \bar{N} \quad (12)$$

where i denotes the imaginary unit,

$$\beta_{i\ell_j} = \frac{2}{\pi c_{i-1}^{-1}} (1 - y^2)^{-1/2} T_i T_\ell T_j dy = \frac{1}{2} \delta_{i,\ell+j} + \frac{1}{c_\ell} (\delta_{i,\ell-j} + \delta_{i,j-\ell})$$

here the following identity is used

$$2T_j T_\ell = T_{j+\ell} + T_{|j-\ell|}.$$

The system of equations (11) and (12) forms an algebraic eigenvalue problem of the following form

$$(A - \lambda B)X = 0 \quad (13)$$

where A and B are known complex square matrices, λ are eigenvalues of the problem under consideration, X are eigenvectors: moreover, λ and X are complex values:

$$\lambda = (\lambda_0, \lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_{2\bar{N}})$$

$$X = \begin{matrix}
 x_{00} & x_{10} & \dots & x_{2\bar{N}+1,0} \\
 x_{01} & x_{11} & \dots & x_{2\bar{N}+1,1} \\
 \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\
 x_{0,2\bar{N}+1} & x_{1,2\bar{N}+1} & \dots & x_{2\bar{N}+1,2\bar{N}+1}
 \end{matrix}$$

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